

Zybertspheres - Spacecraft Flybys

Josef Zybert PhD, Independent Researcher, ZybertCosmology@outlook.com

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In Zybert Cosmology the universe comprises Zybertspheres, \textcircled{Z} . Ours has an antineutron core, enveloped by a matter-antimatter creation zone, enveloped by a growing expanding spherical neutron cloud. Core gravity, \textcircled{a} , is all pervasive affecting all matter and antimatter and light. \textcircled{a} acts radially from \textcircled{Z} centres along the Axis of Zybert causing a δv in spacecraft flybys.

\textcircled{a} manifested as $\textcircled{G}v$, variable part of \textcircled{G} , causes a perturbation of the spacecraft trajectory toward the sun and earth, which changes altitude at perigee, which changes gravity at perigee, which changes velocity at perigee, given by $v^2/r = \textcircled{G}M/r^2$, the perturbation being from $\textcircled{G}v$.

A simulation of a trajectory based on Galileo Flyby 1 [1] has earth at $x=0$ $y=0$, the sun at $x=0$ $y=-1\text{AU}$, Galileo 4 days before perigee and the y -axis along the Axis of Zybert. For $y < -1\text{AU}$ the spacecraft is nudged by $\textcircled{G}v$ toward the sun and to a lesser extent toward earth. For $y > 0$ the spacecraft is nudged toward earth and the sun and at $x=0$, perigee in this geometry, it is closer to earth, in a higher gravity, which increases its velocity given by $v^2/r = \textcircled{G}M/r^2$, by $\text{Sin}(\theta)$ and $\text{Cos}(\theta)$ for the x y components of $\textcircled{G}v$. In this geometry $\delta v = 3.79\text{mm/s}$ [1]. In some geometries/trajectories $\textcircled{G}v$ may cause a higher altitude at perigee. Some graphs from [1] are

Graphs from full spreadsheet simulation [1], in the simulation $\textcircled{G}v$ can be varied from -200% to 200%, and at 0% $\textcircled{G}v=0$ so $\delta v=0$. δv increases as altitude decreases.

[1] Zybertspheres - Phenomena.xlsx see <https://zenodo.org/records/17034092>